

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates:
13 – 29 January 2024

Report published:
January 2025

**Ways of the desert: Conserving Arabian Oryx,
Pharaoh Eagle-owl and other species of the Dubai
Desert Conservation Reserve (DDCR),
United Arab Emirates.**

محمية دبي الصحراوية
DUBAI DESERT CONSERVATION RESERVE

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Conserving Arabian Oryx, Pharaoh Eagle-owl and other species of the
Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve, United Arab Emirates.

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Abstract

The successful collaboration between Biosphere Expeditions and the Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve (DDCR), initiated in 2012, and continued in 2024 with citizen scientists collecting data for the eleventh expedition, from 13 to 29 January 2024.

The 2024 expedition's quadrant surveys recorded the following species from 221 random observations and 61 circular observations: 715 Arabian oryx *Oryx leucoryx*, 620 Arabian gazelles *Gazella arabic*, 190 sand gazelles *Gazella marica*, 2 Arabian hares *Lepus capensis*, 5 Arabian red fox *Vulpes vulpes arabica*, 6 greater hoopoe-larks *Alaemon alaudipes* and 1 pharaoh eagle-owl *Bubo ascalaphus*. Other interesting sightings include one Arabian sand boa *Eryx jayakari* and one Eurasian griffon vulture *Gyps fulvus*.

Population sizes of ungulates are constantly monitored by DDCR staff. Citizen scientists therefore concentrated their surveys on elucidating animal distribution. Arabian oryx is well distributed in the reserve, although it tends to gather in the central and southern areas, especially close to the feeding stations. Arabian gazelle is well spread around the DDCR area, but tends to stay in the gravel plains situated in the centre of the reserve, and around Ghaf groves with shade and irrigation. Sand gazelle is a more timid species that tends to be found away from human activity, mostly in the south of the reserve.

Pharaoh eagle-owl is an important species in the DDCR. A dedicated field signs survey to find animals or their tracks was therefore included in the expedition. From the pre-selected sites, only eight had evidence of the species, and 20 new locations were added as possible areas where the pharaoh eagle-owl could be residing and/or nesting.

A dedicated bird census recorded 45 different species, seven of them invasive, eight rare to sight and four never recorded before. The census highlighted the problem that the DDCR, and the rest of the world, is having with invasive species.

A total of nine camera traps were set up, one of them malfunctioning, and yielded 121 camera trapping days with 11,473 images with 14 species being identified. The three species of ungulates appeared the most. Cryptic species, such as the Arabian hare or the Arabian red fox, were also recorded. In general, camera traps located in isolated areas tended to capture the cryptic species.

Ungulate numbers continue to increase, presenting an overgrazing challenge. Distribution information gathered by the expedition is helpful in mitigation planning. Alternative solutions, such as the reintroduction of predators, are also being considered.

Despite resistance from Biosphere Expeditions and DDCR staff, this joint expedition was forcibly terminated after the 2024 expedition by the Dubai Municipality for not creating any profit for the DDCR. The hypercapitalist folly of expecting profit out of non-profit research and conservation endeavours is self-evident and serves as a classic example of the destructive nature of neoliberal 'profit above everything' thinking.

ملخص

بدأ التعاون الناجح بين بيوسفير اكسبيديشنز ومحمية دبي الصحراوية في عام ٢٠١٢ واستمر في عام ٢٠٢٤ مع قيام العلماء المواطنين بجمع البيانات للبعثة الحادية عشرة، من ١٣ إلى ٢٩ يناير ٢٠٢٤.

سجلت المسوحات الرباعية لبعثة عام ٢٠٢٤ الأنواع التالية من ٢٢١ ملاحظة عشوائية و ٦١ ملاحظة دائرية: ٧١٥ من المها العربي (*Oryx leucoryx*)، و ٦٢٠ من الغزال العربي (*Gazella Arabica*)، و ١٩٠ من الغزال الرملي (*Gazella marica*)، و ٢ من الأرناب البرية (*Lepus capensis*)، و ٥ من الثعلب الأحمر العربي (*Vulpes vulpes arabica*)، و ٦ من طيور الهدد الأكبر (*Alaemon alaudipes*)، و ١ من البوهة الصحراوية (*Bubo ascalaphus*). تشمل المشاهدات الأخرى المثيرة للاهتمام ثعلباً عربياً واحداً، و بوا الرمال العربية (الثعبان الدفان) (*Eryx jayakari*)، وواحدة من نسور الأوراسي (*Gyps fulvus*).

يقوم موظفو محمية دبي الصحراوية بمراقبة أحجام أعداد ذوات الحوافر باستمرار. لذلك ركز العلماء المواطنون مسوحاتهم على توضيح توزيع الحيوانات. ينتشر المها العربي بشكل جيد في المحمية، على الرغم من أنه يميل إلى التجمع في المناطق الوسطى والجنوبية، وخاصة بالقرب من محطات التغذية. ينتشر الغزال العربي بشكل جيد حول منطقة محمية دبي الصحراوية، ولكنه يميل إلى البقاء في السهول الحصوية الواقعة في وسط المحمية، وحول بساتين الغاف مع الظل والري. يعتبر الغزال الرملي من الأنواع الأكثر خجلاً والتي تميل إلى التواجد بعيداً عن النشاط البشري، وخاصة في جنوب المحمية.

البوهة الصحراوية هي نوع مهم في محمية دبي الصحراوية. تم تضمين مسح ميداني مخصص للعثور على الحيوانات أو آثارها في الرحلة الاستكشافية. من بين المواقع المختارة مسبقاً، لم يكن هناك سوى ثمانية مواقع بها أدلة على وجود هذا النوع، وتمت إضافة عشرين موقعاً جديداً كمناطق محتملة حيث يمكن أن تقيم فيها و/أو تعشش فيها البوهة الصحراوية.

سجل تعداد الخاص بالطيور ٤٥ نوعاً مختلفاً، سبعة منها غازية، وثمانية نادرة المشاهدة، وأربعة لم يتم تسجيلها من قبل. سلط التعداد الضوء على المشكلة التي تواجهها محمية دبي الصحراوية وبقية العالم مع الأنواع الغازية.

تم تركيب تسعة كاميرات فخيه، كان أحدها معطلاً، وأسفرت عن ١٢١ يوماً من التسجيلات الفخيه، مع ١١٤٧٣ صورة و تم ١٤ نوعاً منها. ظهرت الأنواع الثلاثة من ذوات الحوافر أكثر من غيرها. كما تم تسجيل الأنواع الخفية، مثل الأرناب البري أو الثعلب الأحمر العربي. بشكل عام، تميل مصائد الكاميرا الموجودة في المناطق المعزولة إلى التقاط الأنواع الخفية.

تستمر أعداد ذوات الحوافر في الزيادة، مما يمثل تحدياً بسبب الإفراط في الرعي. تساعد معلومات التوزيع التي جمعتها البعثة في التخطيط للتخفيف. كما يتم النظر في حلول بديلة، مثل إعادة إدخال الحيوانات المفترسة. وعلى الرغم من مقاومة بيوسفير اكسبيديشنز وموظفي محمية دبي الصحراوية، فقد تم إنهاء هذه البعثة المشتركة قسراً بعد بعثة عام ٢٠٢٤ من قبل بلدية دبي لعدم تحقيق أي ربح لمحمية دبي الصحراوية. إن تأثير الرأسمالية المفرطة المتمثلة في توقع الربح من الجهود الغير ربحية لأعمال البحوث العلمية والصون أمر واضح بذاته ويشكل مثلاً كلاسيكياً للطبيعة المدمرة للتفكير النيوليبرالي "الربح فوق كل شيء".

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1. Expedition review

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Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location, conditions and the general research area are as described in [Sher Shan et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2019\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2018\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2016\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2015\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2014\)](#), [Bell et al. \(2013\)](#).

1.2. Dates & team

The 2024 annual expedition took place over two one-week groups with a team of national and international citizen scientists, professional scientists, and an expedition leader.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities, and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

13 - 20 January 2024: Rachel Blackman (UK), Andrew Collins (UK), Julia Collins (UK), Peter Goodman (UK), Matthias Herold (Germany), Sandra Jablonska (UK), Birgit Käser (Germany), Elisabeth Ladinser (Italy), Jenny Lantair (UK), Elmar Leitgelb (Italy), Georgina Pereira (UAE), Nicola Smith (UK).

22 - 29 January 2024: Francesco Bellezza-Quater (Italy), Ralf Bürglin (Germany), Stephen Crowther (UK), Peter Goodman (UK), Manuela Linke (Germany), Elaine Wilson (UK), Chris Zacharia (UK).

There were also Maria Jose Martin, Basil Roy, Gerhard Erasmus and Aline Witte de la Torre (all of the Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve) as science and support personnel, with Maria Jose Martin acting as principal investigator. The expedition leader was Malika Fettak, assisted by Simon Thomsett, both of Biosphere Expeditions.

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked as there were no incidences.

1.3. Partners

The main partner on this expedition is the Dubai Conservation Board, a government-appointed organisation concerned with the conservation and protection of the Dubai inland desert. Other partners include the National Avian Research Centre.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions, which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as research assistants, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the DDCR and its staff, and the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support. Thank you also to anonymous reviewers for helpful comments on drafts of this report.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

A multimedia expedition diary is available on <https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/arabia-2024/>.

This and all other expedition reports of this and all other expeditions are available on <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Figure 1.5a. Citizen scientists 2024.

1.6. Expedition budget

Each team member paid towards expedition costs a contribution of € 1,880 per person for the 8-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	31,300
Expenditure	
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	5,436
Research includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	945
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis in the UAE	2,844
Expedition base includes all food & services	1,919
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	983
Team recruitment Arabia as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	9,768
Income – Expenditure	9,405
Total percentage spent directly on project	70%

2. Desert species surveys

2.1. Introduction and background

The United Arab Emirates, and Dubai in particular, are well known for their rapid development over the past 40 years, as well as for the mega-construction projects such as the Palm Islands and the Burj Khalifa (the world's tallest building). Less well known is the diversity and beauty of the natural environment, from the dugongs and corals in the Arabian Sea, the flamingos in the khors (inlets) of the coastline, the rugged Hajar mountain range, to the serene splendour of the sandy dune inland desert. Also, little known is that the largest piece of land given to any single project in Dubai was for the establishment of the Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve (DDCR) (Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve, n.d.), at 225 km² or 4.7% of Dubai's total land area.

Previous work from 2012 to 2023 (there were no expeditions in 2021 and 2022 due to the COVID pandemic) and background to the species under investigation are as per [Sher Shan et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2019\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2018\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2016\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2015\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2014\)](#) and [Bell et al. \(2013\)](#). Comparisons will be made to other reports and surveys done by DDCR team or other collaborations.

DEWA ASR

The DDCR has been selected for the world's largest Aquifer Storage and Recovery (ASR) project by DEWA (Dubai Electricity and Water Authority), storing 27 billion litres of water as a strategic reserve in the ground underneath the DDCR. This project has removed and made inaccessible the significant area shown in green on Figure 2.3a from the DDCR and its conservation efforts. It has also created significant noise, air, light and trash pollution.

Survey aims

The 2024 expedition conducted four monitoring surveys:

- Species encounter surveys in quadrants to understand the distribution of the three ungulate species Arabian oryx *Oryx leucoryx*, Arabian gazelle *Gazella arabic*, sand gazelle *Gazella marica* and other target species in DDCR. This also included 'random observations', where any other sightings out of the surveys would be recorded.
- Pharaoh eagle-owl *Bubo ascalaphus* survey to evaluate population status and nesting behaviour.
- Bird Census in Ghaf *Prosopis cineraria* groves to evaluate bird populations in this habitat.
- Camera trapping to record nocturnal and cryptic species.

Survey design and training of citizen scientists

Citizen scientists received species and methodology training at the beginning of each expedition group. Presentations about the identification of ungulates and other target species were part of the training sessions.

Surveys were conducted in four zones, namely north, central, south, and perimeter (Figure 2.3a). Each zone comprised fifteen 2 x 2 km quadrants, with the exception of the north, which had five quadrants affected by the DEWA ASR project. Four of the quadrants in this zone were partial and one of them disappeared due to its location inside the perimeter of the project. In addition, the perimeter zone also has 17 partial quadrants. The total of these 61 quadrants together represent approximately 214 km², or 95%, of the 225 km² of the DDCR and included all key habitats of vegetated dunes, sand dunes and gravel plains.

Figure 2.3a. The DDCR and its survey zones (north = green, central = red, south = orange). The perimeter zone comprises all other zones within the DDCR.

2.2. Methods

Species encounter surveys in quadrants

This method records species encountered during circular observations and random observations. For circular observations, each team of three citizen scientists selected a vantage point within 300 m of the centre of the quadrant marked on their GPS. From this observation point, they recorded all species and their individuals seen by eye, through binoculars, or through camera lenses, for 30 minutes and within 360° (see cover page photo). The survey was conducted between 07:00 and 16:00 over two weeks, covering all 61 quadrants (214 km²).

Random observations were those recorded during the expedition when not conducting any other survey. These observations followed specific conditions, such as not including any invasive species (such as doves *Streptopelia decaocto* or white-eared bulbul *Pycnonotus leucotis*) or groups of ungulates of fewer than seven individuals.

Species observed by both types of surveys were recorded in the datasheets as follows: species name, GPS position of researcher when the species was first seen, time of day when the species was observed, and ecological information such as number of animals (group size), age, behaviour, and any additional comments.

Total number of individuals for each species were then calculated (section 3.5 – total numbers). Ungulate populations are represented in a map generated by QGIS (www.qgis.org).

Pharaoh eagle-owl survey

Although globally assessed as Least Concern (BirdLife International, 2019), the pharaoh eagle-owl is considered Endangered in the UAE (Burfield, et al., 2021) and is one of the target species included in the monitoring programme for the Major Site Values of the DDCR (Simkins, Khafaga, & Sher Shah, 2020). This survey was done for the first time during the 2023 expedition. All previously identified nesting and roosting sites, including the ones from 2023, were revisited. Other preselected locations were included in the survey, comprising a total of 29 locations to check for the presence of pharaoh eagle-owl. The signs used to identify their presence included pellets, nests, or the location of a sighted individual. When found, information such as behaviour (if the animal was seen), location, number of eggs (if a nest was present) and any other comments were noted down.

Bird Census

Point counts methodology with limited distance (Gregory, Gibbons, & Donald, 2004) was used to assess bird populations in Ghaf groves. This survey was carried out in 26 locations, with a total of 96 point counts. Depending on the size of the area, one to seven points were selected to be surveyed. Citizen scientists waited for one minute after arrival to the GPS location before sampling for 10 minutes, recording any species sighted in the surrounding 30 metres (including the number of individuals).

Camera trapping

Nine camera traps (one Reconyx HF2X and eight Bushnell Trophy Cam HD) were deployed during the expedition across the DDCR's four designated zones. Predetermined locations in each of the zones were chosen for the survey groups to set their camera traps.

Camera traps were left out in the field for fifteen days and the SD cards were changed after six days, before the first group of citizen scientists left. All camera traps were set to capture three pictures, with each trigger at a 10 second interval. All nine camera traps used in 2024 were set on natural sites, in the same location as during the 2023 expedition.

2.3. Results

Species encounter surveys in quadrants

A total of 48 species were recorded through random and circular observations: 39 bird species, six mammal species, three reptile species, and two arthropod species (Table 2.3a)

Table 2.3a. Species recorded by the expedition through encounter methods and random observations. Starred* species denotes expedition target species.

Common name	Scientific name	Total individuals
Birds		
Arabian Babbler	<i>Turdoides squamiceps</i>	9
Arabian Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops cyanophrys</i>	15
Asian Desert Warbler	<i>Sylvia nana</i>	2
Brown-necked Raven	<i>Corvus ruficollis</i>	10
Chestnut-bellied Sandgrouse	<i>Pterocles exustus</i>	1
Common Kestrel	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	4
Common Moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	3
Common Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i>	1
Crested Lark	<i>Galerida cristata</i>	8
Desert Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe deserti</i>	14
Eastern Mourning Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe lugens</i>	1
Eurasian Griffon Vulture	<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	1
Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	2
Great Grey Shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>	19
Greater Hoopoe Lark	<i>Alaemon alaudipes</i> *	6
Green-winged Teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	1
Grey Francolin	<i>Ortygornis pondicerianus</i>	34
Grey Heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	6

...continued overleaf

Table 2.3a (continued). Species recorded by the expedition through encounter methods and random observations. Starred* species denotes expedition target species.

Common name	Scientific name	Total individuals
Grey Headed Swamphen	<i>Porphyrio poliocephalus</i>	1
Grey Wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	1
Group: White-eared Bulbul, Desert Wheatear, Arabian Babbler		60
Indian Roller	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	1
Isabelline Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe isabellina</i>	2
Lesser Grey Shrike	<i>Lanius minor</i>	1
Lesser Whitethroat	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	1
Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	3
Long-legged Buzzard	<i>Buteo rufinus</i>	4
Northern Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	1
Pale Crag Martin	<i>Ptyonoprogne obsoleta</i>	2
Pallid Swift	<i>Apus pallidus</i>	3
Pharaoh Eagle-owl	<i>Bubo ascalaphus</i> *	1
Pied Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe pleschanka</i>	3
Red-backed Shrike	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	1
Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	12
Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	11
Swallow	<i>Subtybe unidentified</i>	1
Upcher's Warbler	<i>Hippolais languida</i>	1
Mammals		
Arabian Gazelle	<i>Gazella arabica</i> *	620
Arabian Hare	<i>Lepus capensis</i> *	2
Arabian Oryx	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i> *	725
Arabian Red Fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes arabica</i> *	5
Feral Cat	<i>Felis catus</i>	1
Sand Gazelle	<i>Gazella marica</i> *	190
Reptiles		
Arabian Sand Boa	<i>Eryx jayakari</i>	1
Arabian Sand Skink	<i>Scincus mitranus</i>	1
Spiny-tailed Lizard	<i>Uromastyx aegyptia leptieni</i>	7
Arthropods		
Desert Locust	<i>Schistocerca gregaria</i>	1
Praying Mantis	<i>Mantis religiosa</i>	1

The target species during these surveys were the three species of ungulates (Arabian oryx, Arabian gazelle, and sand gazelle), the Arabian red fox and the Arabian hare. All target species were sighted. Among the ungulates, the Arabian oryx had the highest number of sightings (725), followed by the Arabian gazelle (620), and lastly the sand gazelle (190).

Other target species are more cryptic or nocturnal and were therefore more difficult to sight. This included the Arabian hare (two sightings), the Arabian red fox (five) (Figure 3.1a) and the pharaoh eagle-owl (one). These three species were sighted through random observations. The last species of interest was the Greater Hoopoe-lark, which was sighted six times (Figure 2.3b).

Figure 2.3a. Arabian red fox. © Ralf Bürglin.

Figure 2.3b. Greater hoopoe-lark. © Ralf Bürglin.

Pharaoh eagle-owl

The 29 preselected locations had previously displayed evidence of the presence and/or activity of the pharaoh eagle-owl. These locations corresponded with Ghaf trees and bushes (mostly Firebush *Leptadenia pyrotechnica*) vegetation that is frequently used by the pharaoh eagle-owl. Only eight sites out of the 29 preselected locations had evidence of the pharaoh eagle-owl this year (Table 2.3b). 20 new locations were found with pharaoh eagle-owl evidence. Most of these were located in the northern area of the reserve, in a rocky region called Nazwa. A mix of evidence was gathered by citizen scientists, including fresh and old pellets (Figures 2.3c & d), feathers and an abandoned nest. There were no sightings during the survey, only some tracks left on the top of a dune, which were not confirmed to be from this species.

Figure 2.3c. Multiple owl pellets pictured under a Ghaf tree.

Table 2.3b. Results from the pharaoh eagle-owl survey. New locations and preselected ones with evidence of the presence of the species.

Location	Coordinates	Comments
New	24.83397, 55.69036	Fresh pellets
New	24.88999, 55.66270	3 old pellets found under Ghaf tree
New	24.77979, 55.71719	Fresh pellets
New	24.73567, 55.63599	Fresh pellets
New	24.98566, 55.66242	Prints of a large bird on crest of hill
New	24.98429, 55.66243	Fresh pellets
New	24.98422, 55.66249	Fresh pellets
New	24.98386, 55.66233	Fresh pellets
New	24.99291, 55.66093	Fresh pellets
New	24.99243, 55.66076	Feather
New	24.99043, 55.6607	Feather
New	24.98918, 55.66071	Pellets
New	24.98893, 55.66074	Pellets
New	24.84535, 55.70333	Old pellet under Ghaf tree
New	24.84554, 55.70354	Old pellet under Ghaf tree
New	24.84553, 55.70375	Pellet under Ghaf tree
New	24.84728, 55.687107	Pellet under Ghaf tree
New	24.84488, 55.70358	Pellet under Ghaf tree
New	24.84593, 55.70444	Pellet under Ghaf tree
New	24.84768, 55.70498	Pellet under Ghaf tree
PEO Central 4	24.81463, 55.69984	Fresh pellets
PEO Central 5	24.81463, 55.69989	Large fresh pellets on top of a dune, no prints.
PEO E. Ghaf Grove	24.84558, 55.2036	Abandoned nest. 1 fresh pellet + 1 old pellet found
PEO Perimeter 3	24.73590, 55.63365	Fresh pellets
PEO Perimeter 5	24.74044, 55.73335	Fresh pellets
PEO Ruwayyan	24.89048, 55.66317	3 old pellets. Feather found
PEO S. DEWA1	24.85196, 55.68604	Fresh pellets
PEO Sherpa Camp	24.849633, 55.701355	Fresh pellets

Figure 2.3d. Close-up picture of an owl pellet.

Bird census

A total of 45 different species were recorded during the bird census (Table 2.3c): seven of them were invasive species, eight species were rare to be sighted and four species had never previously been recorded in the reserve. The rest of the species (26) were common in the DDCR.

The three species with the highest number of individuals recorded were invasive species: the Eurasian collared dove (1156), house sparrow (391) and white-eared bulbul (157).

Table 2.3c. Species recorded by bird census throughout the expedition.

Common name	Scientific name	Status	Total Individuals
Arabian Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Rare	1
African Stonechat	<i>Saxicola torquatus</i>	Rare	1
Alpine Swift	<i>Tachymarptis melba</i>	New record	1
Arabian Babbler	<i>Turdoides squamiceps</i>	Common	47
Asian Desert Warbler	<i>Sylvia nana</i>	Common	1
Barn Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Common	1
Black Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	Common	7
Blue-cheeked Bee-eater	<i>Merops persicus</i>	Common	2
Brown-necked Raven	<i>Corvus ruficollis</i>	Common	2
Chestnut-bellied Sandgrouse	<i>Pterocles exustus</i>	Common	55
Common Moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Common	2
Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Invasive	26
Common Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i>	Common	10
Common Swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	Common	1
Crested Lark	<i>Galerida cristata</i>	Common	1
Desert Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe deserti</i>	Common	12
Desert Whitethroat	<i>Sylvia minula</i>	Rare	1
Eastern Orphean Warbler	<i>Sylvia crassirostris</i>	New record	2
Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Invasive	1156
Eurasian Stonechat	<i>Saxicola rubicola</i>	New record	2
Graceful Prinia	<i>Prinia gracilis</i>	Common	3
Great Grey Shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>	Common	45
Green-winged Teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Common	5
Grey Francolin	<i>Ortygornis pondicerianus</i>	Common	47
Grey Heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Common	3
House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Invasive	391
Indian Silverbill	<i>Euodice malabarica</i>	Common	3
Isabelline Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe isabellina</i>	Rare	4
Laughing Dove	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>	Invasive	137
Lesser Whitethroat	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	Common	7
Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	Common	2

...continued overleaf

Table 2.3c (continued). Species recorded by bird census throughout the expedition.

Common name	Scientific name	Status	Total individuals
Long-legged Buzzard	<i>Buteo rufinus</i>	Common	1
Pied Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe pleschanka</i>	Rare	1
Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	Rare	11
Red-backed Shrike	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	Rare	1
Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	Common	31
Rock Dove (Feral Pigeon)	<i>Columba livia</i>	Invasive	83
Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Invasive	3
Spotted Flycatcher	<i>Muscicapa striata</i>	Common	1
Squacco Heron	<i>Ardeola ralloides</i>	New record	1
Swift	<i>Subtype unidentified</i>	Common	1
Tawny Pipit	<i>Anthus campestri</i>	Rare	1
Upcher's Warbler	<i>Hippolais languida</i>	Common	15
White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	Common	3
White-eared Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i>	Invasive	157

Camera traps

121 camera trapping days captured 11,473 images. 2,455 of these images contained recognisable subjects, of which 2,102 were of native fauna and 353 were of humans or vehicles (Figures 2.3e & f). Fourteen wildlife species could be identified from the trapping effort. One of the nine traps set malfunctioned. During the first week, the camera trap was triggered every 5 seconds by a shrub, causing the SD card to run out of memory space after 12 hours. During the second week, the camera trap did not record any footage.

Six mammal species were recorded (Table 2.3d). Arabian gazelles were the most abundant, with 168 individuals recorded across eight traps. Arabian oryx were the second most abundant species, with 102 individuals pictured across six camera traps. Forty-three sand gazelle individuals were recorded across seven traps, 16 Arabian red fox individuals across five traps (Figure 2.3g), and 13 Arabian hare individuals were recorded by camera traps 14 and 18 (Figure 2.3h). One Cheesman's gerbil was recorded on camera trap 19 as the camera trap was unintentionally placed in front of its burrow (Figure 2.3i).

Seven bird species were recorded (Table 2.3d). Three Arabian babblers, one brown-necked raven, two desert wheatears, five grey francolins, two house sparrows, 47 Eurasian collared doves and three laughing doves were all recorded across 4 different camera trap locations.

One reptile species was recorded on camera trap 18, the Arabian sand skink.

Total number of images = 11,473

Figure 2.3e. Proportion of each type of picture depending on the object captured.

Total number of images = 11,473

Figure 2.3f. Camera trapping results as a pie chart.

Table 2.3d. Results of camera trapping in 2024, the total number of animals counted in images.

Species	Images recorded	% of Images	Total no. of animals in images
Arabian oryx	608	28.92	102
Arabian gazelle	598	28.45	168
Sand gazelle	269	12.80	43
Arabian red fox	48	2.28	16
Arabian hare	120	5.71	13
Cheesman's gerbil	231	10.99	1
Grey francolin	9	0.43	5
Brown-necked raven	3	0.14	1
Arabian babbler	9	0.43	3
Desert wheatear	6	0.29	2
Eurasian collared dove	179	8.52	47
Laughing dove	9	0.43	3
House sparrow	10	0.47	2
Arabian Sand Skink	3	0.14	1
Total	2,102	100%	407

Figure 2.3g. Arabian red fox captured by camera trap 17.

Figure 2.3h. Arabian hare captured by camera trap 14.

Figure 2.3i. A single Cheesman’s gerbil captured by camera trap 19.

Overall count of all species found during the expedition

A total of 76 different species were recorded in the reserve in 2024: 64 bird species, seven mammal species, three reptile species and two arthropod species (Table 2.3e).

The most numerous species were the Eurasian collared dove (1,156 individuals), the Arabian oryx (725 individuals) and the Arabian gazelle (620 individuals).

Table 2.3e. Species recorded during the expedition. “Total number of individuals” includes all the individuals recorded by species encounter, random observations and bird census. “Camera traps” includes the species and their numbers extracted from camera trapping. Starred* includes animals sighted out of all these methods.

Common name	Scientific name	Total individuals	Camera traps
African Stonechat	<i>Saxicola torquatus</i>	1	
Alpine Swift	<i>Tachymarptis melba</i>	1	
Arabian Babbler	<i>Turdoides squamiceps</i>	56	3
Arabian Gazelle	<i>Gazella arabica</i>	620	168
Arabian Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops cyanophrys</i>	15	
Arabian Hare	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	2	13

...continued overleaf

Table 2.3e (continued). Species recorded during the expedition.

Common name	Scientific name	Total individuals	Camera traps
Arabian Oryx	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i>	725	102
Arabian Red Fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes arabica</i>	5	16
Arabian Sand Boa	<i>Eryx jayakari</i>	1	
Arabian Sand Skink	<i>Scincus mitranus</i>	1	1
Asian Desert Warbler	<i>Sylvia nana</i>	3	
Barn Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	1	
Black Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	7	
Blue-cheeked Bee-eater	<i>Merops persicus</i>	2	
Brown-necked Raven	<i>Corvus ruficollis</i>	12	1
Cheesman's Gerbil	<i>Gerbillus cheesmani</i>		1
Chestnut-bellied Sandgrouse	<i>Pterocles exustus</i>	56	
Common Kestrel	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	4	
Common Moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	5	
Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	26	
Common Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i>	11	
Common Swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	1	
Crested Lark	<i>Galerida cristata</i>	9	
Desert Locust	<i>Schistocerca gregaria</i>	1	
Desert Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe deserti</i>	26	2
Desert Whitethroat	<i>Silvia minula</i>	1	
Eastern Mourning Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe lugens</i>	1	
Eastern Orphean Warbler	<i>Sylvia crassirostris</i>	2	
Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	1156	47
Eurasian Griffon Vulture	<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	1	
Eurasian Stonechat	<i>Saxicola rubicola</i>	2	
Feral Cat	<i>Felis catus</i>	1	
Graceful Prinia	<i>Prinia gracilis</i>	3	
Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	2	
Great Grey Shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>	64	
Greater Hoopoe Lark	<i>Alaemon alaudipes</i>	6	
Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	1	
Green-winged Teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	6	
Grey Francolin	<i>Ortygornis pondicerianus</i>	81	5
Grey Heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	9	
Grey Headed Swamphen	<i>Porphyrio poliocephalus</i>	1	
Grey Wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	1	

...continued overleaf

Table 2.3e (continued). Species recorded during the expedition.

Common name	Scientific name	Total individuals	Camera traps
Group: White-eared Bulbul, Desert Wheatear, Arabian Babbler		60	
House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	391	2
Indian Roller	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	1	
Indian Silverbill	<i>Euodice malabarica</i>	3	
Isabelline Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe isabellina</i>	6	
Laughing Dove	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>	137	3
Lesser Grey Shrike	<i>Lanius minor</i>	1	
Lesser Whitethroat	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	8	
Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	5	
Long-eared Owl *	<i>Asio otus</i>	1	
Long-legged Buzzard	<i>Buteo rufinus</i>	5	
Northern Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	1	
Pale Crag Martin	<i>Ptyonoprogne obsoleta</i>	2	
Pallid Swift	<i>Apus pallidus</i>	3	
Pharaoh Eagle-owl	<i>Bubo ascalaphus</i>	1	
Pied Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe pleschanka</i>	4	
Praying Mantis	<i>Mantis religiosa</i>	1	
Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	11	
Red-backed Shrike	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	2	
Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	43	
Rock Dove (Feral Pigeon)	<i>Columba livia</i>	83	
Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	14	
Sand Gazelle	<i>Gazella marica</i>	190	43
Spiny-tailed Lizard	<i>Uromastix aegyptia leptieni</i>	7	
Spotted Flycatcher	<i>Muscicapa striata</i>	1	
Squacco Heron	<i>Ardeola ralloides</i>	1	
Swallow	<i>Subtype unidentified</i>	1	
Swift	<i>Subtype unidentified</i>	1	
Tawny Pipit	<i>Anthus campestris</i>	1	
Upcher's Warbler	<i>Hippolais languida</i>	15	
White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	3	
White-eared Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i>	157	

This list includes a new sighting for the DDCR of a long-eared Owl *Asio otus* (Figures 2.3i & j). This sighting took place outside of the surveys, during the last morning of the first expedition group in the reserve.

Figure 2.3j. Long-eared owl *Asio otus*. © Matthias Herold.

Figure 2.3k. Long-eared owl *Asio otus*. © Matthias Herold.

2.4. Discussion

Species encounter surveys in quadrants

Weekly counts are carried out by DDCR staff on the main roads of the reserve where the feeding stations are located. The results received from the weekly counts (corresponding to the expedition's dates) for the three ungulate species were 546 Arabian oryx, 646 Arabian gazelles and 234 sand gazelles.

When comparing the DDCR staff weekly counts with the expedition results (Figure 2.4a), there is not much difference, with the exception of the Arabian oryx. Higher differences were expected between the counts, as the DDCR only carries them out on the main roads, while the citizen scientists carried out their surveys in more remote areas. The expedition results do, however, correlate more with the dynamics of the three ungulates in the reserve as the Arabian oryx is the most numerous species, followed by the Arabian gazelle and finally the sand gazelle.

Figure 2.4a. Comparison of ungulate counts between DDCR staff weekly count and expedition results.

The rest of the species recorded are common in the DDCR, with the exception of the eastern mourning wheatear *Oenanthe lugens*, which has never been recorded before in the reserve. The closest sightings of this species are from rocky areas in Abu Dhabi. Due to the lack of pictures to confirm the sighting, this species will not be recognised as a new species in the DDCR Bird Checklist.

The spiny-tailed lizard *Uromastyx aegyptia leptieni* (Figure 2.4b) is a species of reptile that lives in the gravel plains of the reserve. This species is more active during warm months (May – August) (Wilms, Wagner, Shobrak, & Bohme, 2009). Activity decreases with lower temperatures. When this expedition took place in January of 2023, the average temperature in the DDCR was 18.7°C (Dubai Municipality, 2023). According to DDCR team observations, during this month the activity of the spiny-tailed lizard is very reduced and it is therefore very rare to observe them out of the burrow. However, during the January 2024 expedition, several individuals were observed during the surveys. High temperatures and increased rainfall during this month, and the precursory months, could have been the reason for this activity.

Figure 2.4b. Spiny-tailed lizard out of its burrow. © Ralf Bürglin.

Pharaoh eagle-owl

Most of the literature about the pharaoh eagle-owl has been focused on the diet of this species. However, in the DDCR specific surveys related to the habitat preference or brooding behaviour of the pharaoh eagle-owl are conducted. In January 2022, conservation officers found a nest in a Firebush (Roy & D'Silva, 2022). This nest has not been used again, most likely because the nest was raided after the second round of nesting in the same season (evidence of broken eggs was found in the area). There were no findings of active nests during the 2023 expedition. During the 2024 expedition, only eight of the 29 preselected sights had some evidence of pharaoh eagle-owl. However, 20 new sites were recorded with evidence of pharaoh eagle-owl, which highlights the bigger range of this species.

Figure 2.4c shows most of the new sites with pharaoh eagle-owl evidence are located in the north of the reserve. This is plausible since this species has been observed mostly in rocky areas with crevices (Moldovan & D Sandor, 2009), (Abi-Said, Al Zein, Abu Baker, & Amr, 2020). Other observations made by DDCR staff confirm the presence of pharaoh eagle-owl in Nazwa Mountain. This was unexpected since the DEWA ASR project causes significant noise and light disturbance near the observation sites.

No nests were found by the expedition, although during the first expedition group the DDCR team found an active nest with three chicks that has been monitored since its discovery (Figure 2.4d).

Figure 2.4c. Map of the locations with evidence of the pharaoh eagle-owl.

Figure 2.4d. Pharaoh eagle-owl owlets. © Ralf Bürglin.

Bird census

A bird census was performed for the first time in the reserve. The DDCR bird checklist compiles all the bird species recorded throughout the years during random observations. The goal of this survey was to find the species that inhabit and, possibly, nest in the Ghaf trees, in collaboration with the research project of one of the DDCR Conservation Officers (“Biodiversity in Ghaf Trees (*Prosopis cineraria* (L.) Druce) with focus on bird nesting”). 58% of the species found during the bird census are common in the reserve, with the three most numerous species being invasive species (Figure 2.4e). These results will aid the DDCR in identifying the locations with the biggest bird populations and in developing a management plan to remove pests, or at least reduce their populations.

There are six species of water birds (12%) whose presence in the desert environment can be explained by the existence of artificial lakes.

The four species that were recorded for the first time in the DDCR have been recorded previously in UAE. Some of the records could be expected, since other sightings of these species are from areas close to the DDCR. However, Alpine swift is a vagrant species that has been sighted in Abu Dhabi, never in Dubai. Similarly, the eastern Orphean warbler is a migratory species that has been sighted in Abu Dhabi and Fujairah Emirates, but never in Dubai. However, the DDCR does not recognise these sightings as the pictures provided were not clear enough to identify the individuals with confidence and the two species can be easily confused with other species more common in the area.

Figure 2.4e. Categories of birds from the DDCR Checklist.

Camera trapping

121 camera trapping days captured 11,473 images, with a total of 14 species identified (Table 2.4a). The results from the three ungulates were expected, since they are the most numerous and conspicuous. Other cryptic species, such as the Arabian hare or the Cheesman’s gerbil, were captured, highlighting the importance of the use of camera traps as a conservation measure. These species are nocturnal and shy, which, unless trapped, makes it hard to evaluate their presence and/or behavioural patterns. As a result, these species are expected to appear in more isolated areas or in the south of the reserve, where human presence is lower. Conversely, species such as the Arabian oryx or Arabian gazelle were expected to appear anywhere, as they are more used to human presence, and they have been previously reported in all areas of the DDCR. Their presence could, however, be lower close to tour operator camps, which cause disturbance.

The Arabian hare was captured by cameras 14 and 18, which are located in the south and in an isolated point in the central area, respectively (Figure 2.4f). All pictures were taken at night, which matches with this species’ behavioural activity.

The Arabian red fox appeared in cameras set up in different areas of the reserve, and their distribution did not follow any pattern of isolation or human activity. In the DDCR, human activity is decreased at night as groups are concentrated in the different camps. During the day the presence of cars and people are more distributed and human activity is therefore increased. The widespread presence of the Arabian red fox is positive as it indicates a large, healthy population that is not affected by human disturbance.

Camera traps 11 and 18, due to their more isolated locations, were expected to have higher activity. Number 11, however, was one of the camera traps with the lowest number of recordings (20 Arabian gazelles, nine sand gazelles and one desert wheatear). The reason for this could be that the area is barely vegetated and there is a more appealing Ghaf grove close by (Tawi Ruwayyan), with irrigation and shade. Camera trap 15 was set there, which captured more pictures with ungulates and also recorded an Arabian red fox. By contrast, Camera trap 18 met expectations, as two cryptic species were recorded (the Arabian red fox and the Arabian hare).

Figure 2.4f. Camera traps locations.

Figure 2.4g. Image from camera trap 11.

Figure 2.4h. Image from camera trap 15.

Figure 2.4i. Camera trap 18 showing an Arabian hare at night.

Table 2.4a. Camera trapping (CT) results by number of individuals captured.

Trap number	Latitude	Longitude	Arabian oryx	Arabian gazelle	Sand gazelle	Arabian red fox	Arabian Hare	Cheesmans gerbil	Arabian babbler	Brown-necked raven	Desert wheatear	Grey francolin	House sparrow	Eurasian collared dove	Laughing dove	Arabian sand skink
CT 11	55.655953	24.904303	0	20	9	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
CT 14	55.69399	24.76274	19	22	15	1	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CT 15	55.665463	24.900862	6	32	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0
CT 16	55.660494	24.869189	5	19	10	5	0	0	3	0	0	1	2	36	3	0
CT 17	55.65594	24.850245	24	31	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CT 18	55.626555	24.819682	0	3	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
CT 19	55.703251	24.820728	8	33	2	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	11	0	0
CT 20	55.616534	24.779901	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CT Rex 1	55.647524	24.766422	40	8	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Total	102	168	43	16	13	1	3	1	2	5	2	47	3	1

Camera traps set up in the south (CT14 and CT Rex1) were also expected to have higher activity than the rest. CT Rex1 was located next to a Ghaf grove and was therefore irrigated and shaded, with a slightly higher presence of humans due to the maintenance of the solar panels located there. CT14 was set up in an area that corresponded with a gravel plain, away from the roads and behind dunes. Both camera traps showed high activity, capturing all three species of ungulates, Arabian red fox, and Arabian hare. This activity can be explained by the remote location and the richness of bushes.

Figure 2.4j. Image from Camera Trap 14.

There was a high presence of invasive species (house sparrow, Eurasian-collared dove and laughing dove) at CT16 and CT19 due to its location inside a Ghaf grove.

These results highlight the importance of the use of the camera traps in research. It is a non-invasive measure that does not affect the movement of animals. It also allows the monitoring of nocturnal and/or cryptic species and helps to determine if there are any areas where human presence is affecting wildlife and should therefore be reduced.

Figure 2.4k. Image from Camera Trap Rex1.

Figure 2.4l. Ghaf grove from Camera Trap 16.

Figure 2.4m. Gravel plain in front of Ghaf grove (Camera Trap 19).

Figure 2.4n. Image from Camera Trap 17 - Arabian gazelle getting very close to the camera.

Overall counting of species

Around 142 bird species have been recorded in the DDCR (Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve, n.d.). During the 2024 expedition, citizen scientists found a total of 64 bird species (45% of the total), including those species recorded, but not recognised by the DDCR due to a lack of pictures.

The distribution and dynamics of ungulates are of utmost importance as, depending on their location, some habitats can be impacted, for example through overgrazing.

Arabian gazelles are the smallest of the two gazelles within the reserve, however they have the biggest numbers. In the DDCR, the last report about their distribution (Erasmus, Roy, Witte de la Torre, Martin, & Madurapperuma, 2023) established that Arabian gazelles tend to gather mostly in the centre of the reserve (gravel plains from Al Maha Resort area). There are smaller groups in the northern areas and very few in the south of the reserve. These counts were performed on the reserve's main roads, whereas citizen scientists' counts were carried out at 61 different points, most of which were in remote areas. The results from the expedition therefore show a more detailed distribution of this species within the reserve. As previously suggested, Arabian gazelles did prefer areas that were located in the centre of the reserve, with gravel plains. They also tended to gather at a northern point of the reserve, with planted trees and irrigation. Lower densities were recorded in the south of the reserve. Since these are the results of an intensive 10-day data collection effort, they help to establish the Arabian gazelle's dynamics and movement patterns (Figure 2.4o).

In the case of sand gazelles, they are sparsely distributed, mostly in the south of the reserve (Figure 2.4p). They are the most timid of the three ungulates and tend to shy away from any human activity. This is why they are predominantly found in the quieter south of the reserve, with only a few individuals travelling to the busier north. This differs from the results obtained from the DDCR survey (Erasmus, Roy, Witte de la Torre, Martin, & Madurapperuma, 2023), where a wider distribution of sand gazelles was recorded. This difference could be due to the fact that during the DDCR survey all individuals were counted, whereas the expedition was tasked to count sand gazelles during circular observations and only to note them down as random observations when a group of seven or more was found. Sand gazelles are more solitary and do not tend to gather in big groups, which could have therefore contributed to the narrower distribution recorded by the citizen scientists (Figure 4.5b). More research is needed to get to the bottom of this.

The Arabian oryx is the largest ungulate inside the reserve and has the biggest population. They are observed everywhere in the reserve in winter, although in summer they tend to gather close to the waterholes and shaded areas (Figure 2.4q). They are used to human activity, although it has been observed that individuals in the southern area tend to be slightly more timid. These DDCR staff observations correspond with the results obtained by the expedition. Solitary individuals are normally males roaming around; females tend to be in bigger groups with their calves. The range of individuals in the herds recorded was 9-15, and they tended to roam around the central and southern parts of the reserve. Bigger herds also roamed around the same areas, whereas single individuals or small groups were found in areas where human activity was higher.

Another interesting record is the sighting of the Arabian sand boa *Eryx jayakari* preying on an Arabian sand skink *Scincus mitranus* during the daytime (Figure 2.4r). The Arabian sand boa is a nocturnal reptile that usually burrows deep into the sand during the day; however, it can still be out early in the morning, which is when it was found by one of the expedition teams.

Figure 2.4o. Distribution and density of Arabian gazelle in the DDCR.

Figure 2.4p. Distribution and density of sand gazelle in the DDCR.

Figure 2.4q. Distribution and density of Arabian oryx in the DDCR.

Figure 2.4r. Arabian sand boa *Eryx jayakari* strangulating an Arabian sand skink *Scincus mitranus* © Ralf Bürglin.

Overall conclusions

The conservation success of Arabian oryx and with it their multiplication in the reserve is a challenge, as numbers keep increasing, jeopardising the overall health of the ecosystem through overgrazing and other effects. Thanks to more extensive research programmes, such as the one carried out by Biosphere Expeditions, the DDCR can assess where the population of this ungulate is concentrated in order to focus conservation measures there.

Bird surveys are challenging, even to bird-watchers. In this context, the results obtained by the citizen scientists are remarkable and plausible and highlights the challenge the DDCR is facing with invasive species. More extensive research focusing on invasive species is needed in order to evaluate solutions.

The presence of the pharaoh eagle-owl, especially in Nazwa, is a very positive sign, as one of the main disruptors of wildlife activity is human activity. Despite an external project being carried out with high human disturbance, the pharaoh eagle-owl was sighted in a rocky area. This unexpected sighting was backed up by signs of pharaoh eagle-owl activity, recorded by citizen scientists on this expedition.

Camera traps are continuously successful, not only observing cryptic species, but also confirming that human activity is not impacting these species as much as was previously thought.

In this context, and given all the other achievements of the expeditions over the years, as for example showcased in the DDCR museum, it is especially unfortunate that despite resistance from Biosphere Expeditions and the DDCR, this joint expedition was terminated after the 2024 expedition by the Dubai Municipality for not creating any profit for the DDCR. The hypercapitalist folly of expecting profit out of non-profit research and conservation endeavours is self-evident and serves as a classic example of the destructive nature of neoliberal 'profit above everything' thinking. Biosphere Expeditions wishes the DDCR and its staff all the best for their conservation endeavours, especially in the light of external pressures such as the DEWA ASR mentioned in this report. The DDCR is a special place, which deserves to be maintained and supported as is, without any further interference from hypercapitalist or other egregious powers.

2.5. Literature cited

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